

Radiation Biomedicine: A Brief Introduction

Abhay Kumar Pandey

Department of Physiology, All India Institute of Medical Sciences, BHOPAL, Madhya Pradesh, India.

*Corresponding author: E-mail: erjyotsna@gmail.com

Received: February 2, 2015, Accepted: April 2, 2015, Published: April 2, 2015.

ABSTRACT

Radiation and radioactive substances are permanent features of environment and exposure to them can not be totally avoided, but limited. Biomedical uses of radiation as well as their application in industry and agriculture distinguish current human development. There is crucial need for understanding the biomedical interaction of diverse kind of radiation under diverse modes, toward smooth use without risks, which are quite serious. This article briefly introduces the perspective of radiation biomedicine toward such end among both the biomedical and general community.

Keyword: Radiation biology, Radioactivity, Radiology, Health effects of radiation

INTRODUCTION

Mankind is exposed to radiation arising on earth and from the cosmos. New challenges are emerging in biological consequences due to increasing radiation exposures globally. Exposures like, radiowaves, microwaves, ultra violet rays, X rays, Gamma rays, come under the spectrum of electromagnetic radiation. Each differ in wavelength and the amount of energy transferred. Their penetration and heating impact through objects including living cells depend on the referred characteristics. Electromagnetic radiation is made of bundles of energy particles, called photons, that travel by speed of light [1]

Ionizing Radiation

Ionizing radiation is the one, possessing enough energy to knock out electrons from atoms. This results in generation of ions. Spontaneous disintegration of atoms with release of particulate energy (neutrons, beta and alpha particles), or electromagnetic waves (Gamma rays, X rays) is described as radioactivity. The released energy has ionization potential. If properly contained, the ionizing radiation is beneficially applicable in medical, industrial, agricultural and disease research tasks. When uncontrolled, it is health hazard.

The alpha particles are positively charged, coarse energy particles. Their penetrability is poor but potential to harm tissues as skin, respiratory epithelium, bone marrow etc through usual routes of exposure is high. Masks and other filters of radioactive dust can ward off alpha particles. The beta particles are electrons, essentially. They can go long distances through air and have higher skin penetrance. Mere sheet of plastic may shield against them, however. The Gamma and X rays are pure photons. Gamma rays, with significant energy content have high harming potential. X rays have less energy, penetrate soft tissues but are hindered by bones.

Non Ionizing Radiation

These are weak energy radiations unable to induce ionization, but merely cause atoms to vibrate within molecules. The sound

waves, visible light, microwaves are such examples. Typically these radiations have low frequency and large wave lengths. Microwaves find application in heating food, telecommunication etc. The infra red radiation is also used to warm food in restaurants. Radio waves with wave lengths between 1 to 100 meters and frequencies between 1 to 100 million Hertz, are employed for broadcasting. [2].

Sources of Radiation

The radiation from Sun and stars is termed cosmic and risk of exposure increases in prolonged high altitude flights. Terrestrial radiation emanates from radioactive materials present in soil, rocks, water etc. Air contains Radon while organic plant and animal matters bear radioactive Carbon and Potassium. Different geographic locations may differ up to 200 times the average global radiation exposures. Coastal Kerala and parts of Tamil Nadu in India have highest background Gamma rays and Radon exposure levels. Internal radiation refers to that arising from constitutive radioactive carbon and potassium, through the life.

Anthropogenic radiation [3] results from deliberate human endeavours including, medical procedures, both diagnostic and therapeutic; consumer entities as television, cell phones, fuels (gas and coal); building materials etc. Less than one in thousand quantity of radiation exposure results on average from the nuclear exercises.

Biological Consequences of Ionizing Radiation [4-6]

The energy delivered by ionizing radiation can have graded dose dependant severity of adverse effects, called deterministic effects. There can also be threshold dependant probability of adverse effect (stochastic effect). The latter involve effects like genetic alteration, cancer production, that occur in independent cells, whose number increases with increase in exposure. The deterministic effects are damages to cells and cell death at higher exposure thresholds. Stochastic consequences occur at much lower exposure levels also. The radiation impact depends on several

factors. These include, the kind of (alpha, beta, gamma) radiation; amount of exposure; rate of exposure; part of body exposed; sudden (acute) or gradual regular low level exposure for long; age of the subject exposed etc. Cancer induction by ionizing radiation is quite well known. It may be possible that low radiation exposures can stimulate repair process of damaged DNA and production of antioxidant defence enzymes. Biological effects simply form three patterns [7,8]. There can be total repair of radiation induced cell injury. The damaged cells may die and be replaced by healthy cells. There may however be an imperfect repair and persistence of change inflicted by radiation. The cells may replicate to generate biophysically different cell.

Limiting Radiation Exposure

The system of limiting radiation exposure is based on recommendations of International Commission on Radiological Protection (ICRP) [9]. The maximum permissible dose for occupational exposure is 20 mSv per year, averaged for successive five years (i.e. total 100 mSv in 5 years), with no more than 50 mSv exposure in any single year. Average exposure for public is permissible under 1 mSv per year, averaged over five years, over and above the background radiation and excluding medical exposures.

Lead is particularly well suited to shield from effects of Gamma rays and X rays [10]. This is due to high atomic number of lead (made of number of protons, with corresponding number of electrons). The electrons block the Gamma rays and X rays, proportionate to thickness of the shield. Lead does not protect against uncharged neutron radiation. Materials with low atomic number elements as Hydrogen, water are better suited to serve as neutron shields. They form interactive cross sections with neutrons. Low density materials may however, while blocking neutrons emit Gamma rays. Combination of both high and low atomic number elements would meet the task better.

Epilogue

Radiology is vital diagnostic tool. Most disposable medical accessories and supplies are usable because they can be sterilized by radiation. Radiotherapy is the common mode of cancer treatment. Nuclear techniques are increasingly applied in industry, for examining integrity of engineering structures especially examining cracks and welds. Irradiation is also

important means of preserving foodstuff and wastage reduction. Diseases carried by insects and afflictions are removed. The Radiation risk is conditional to reap benefits of the science and technology of radiation. Radiation safety standards are based on experience accrued through using the technology, understanding of health effects and structural and operational safety designs.

REFERENCES:

1. Radiation quantities and units of ionizing radiation. <http://www.ccohs.ca/ashanswers/phys-agents/ionizing.html> dt 15 Dec 2014
2. Ronca D. How radiation works? <http://science.howstuffworks.com/radiation2.htm> dt 15 Dec 2014
3. Reactor Concepts Manual. Natural and manmade radiation sources. USNRC Technical Training Centre. 6-1 0703 <http://www.nic.gov/reading-rm/basic-ref/teachers/06.pdf> dt 15 Dec 2014
4. Little MP, Wakeford R, Tawn EJ, Bouffler SD, de Gonzalez BA Risks associated with low doses and low dose rates of ionizing radiation: Why linearity may be (almost) the best we can do. *Radiology* 2009 251 :6-12
5. Willers H, Held KD Introduction to clinical radiation biology. *Hematol oncol Clin north Am* 2006 20 :1-24
6. Riley PA Free radicals in biology: oxidative stress and the effects of ionizing radiation *Int J Radiat Biol* 1994 65 :27-33
7. Luckey T D Biological effects of ionizing radiation: a perspective for Japan *J Am Physicians and Surgeons* 2011 16 :45-46
8. Preston R J USEPA NCHPS March 2012: Radiation protection and tissue reactions: an ICRP position <http://hpschapters.org/northcarolina/spring2012/preston-radiation%20protection%20tissue%20reaction.pdf>
9. International Commission on Radiological Protection <http://www.irpa.net/page.asp?id=545021crp>

Citation: Abhay Kumar Pandey (2015). Radiation Biomedicine: A Brief Introduction J. of Advancement in Medical and Life Sciences. V2I4. DOI: 10.15297/JALS.V2I4.03

Copyright: © 2015 Abhay Kumar Pandey. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.